

Planar Filter for Microwave Loss Analysis in Nickel and Cobalt Ferrite Samples

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the microwave loss behavior of nickel ferrite (NFO) and cobalt ferrite (CFO) samples using a planar fractal filter, along with the study of the crystal lattice of each sample. The resonator geometry used is the fourth iteration of the Hilbert fractal. The Hilbert curve is employed to compress the filter area and increase the interaction area with the tested sample. The resonance frequency is approximately 1.1 GHz, within the range of 0.7 to 1.6 GHz. Filter measurements were conducted with samples of each material to evaluate their specific characteristics.

Keywords: cobalt ferrite, filter, losses, microwave, nickel ferrite

1. Introduction

Lossy materials have been extensively studied in the telecommunications field across various frequency ranges. These materials are capable of dissipating incident electromagnetic energy through energy conversion processes, rather than reflecting or transmitting it back into the environment [1]. This property makes them indispensable in applications where reducing unwanted reflections enhances the performance of communication systems. Additionally, they are used in security and camouflage applications, where dissipating electromagnetic energy helps minimize the detection of objects by radar systems and other remote sensing devices [1].

In microwaves, materials contain molecules or atoms that vibrate readily, particularly at the frequency of the incident microwaves, leading to more efficient dissipation. [2]. This characteristic is determined by the energy required to excite these vibrations and the molecular structure of the material. The amplitude of these vibrations is related to the stiffness of the material's structure, which in turn is influenced

by the spacing between atoms. In materials with larger atomic spacing, greater vibration amplitudes are allowed, favoring higher microwave loss. Conversely, materials with smaller atomic spacing have more intense interatomic forces, which restrict vibration amplitudes and may reduce efficiency [3].

Spinel ferrite with the general formula AB_2O_4 represents a large group of oxides with numerous electromagnetic applications, ranging from low wavelengths to microwaves, including electronic devices [4]. Nanostructured spinel has been applied as magnetic fluids, in drug delivery, microwave devices, antenna devices, magnetic recording devices, and magnetic sensors, among others [5,6]. Spinel ferrite belongs to the $Fd-3m$ space group with cubic symmetry. These materials are stable systems, demonstrating a good degree of loss and reflection of electromagnetic radiation in the microwave range.

Nickel ferrite is a magnetic material with an inverse spinel structure, where iron and nickel ions occupy distinct positions

within the crystal lattice. It has favorable electrical and chemical properties, as well as high stability. Its primary uses include photocatalysis for the degradation of contaminants, electrocatalysis for the detection of chemical substances, and

adsorption for the removal of heavy metals and dyes from polluted water. The efficiency in some of these applications can be enhanced by combining it with other materials [7].

Cobalt ferrite has distinct physical and mechanical characteristics, making it useful in nanomedicine. It is a robust magnetic material with a high Curie temperature (520°C), significant coercivity, moderate magnetization (around 80 emu/g at room temperature), high constant anisotropy and notable magnetostriction. It also has good chemical stability, mechanical durability, wear resistance, simple synthesis, and electrical insulation. These properties make cobalt ferrite suitable for medical applications like magnetic drug delivery, radio-frequency hyperthermia, MRI, and medical diagnostics [8].

Nickel and cobalt ferrites are particularly advantageous for microwave applications due to their magnetic properties and ability to attenuate electromagnetic waves, which can reduce interference and enhance device efficiency. Additionally, the thermal and chemical stability of these ferrites contributes to reliable performance in varying conditions [9].

The use of renewable polymers, such as cashew gum, in the synthesis of these ferrites aligns with the principles of green chemistry, which emphasize atomic economy and the use of safe solvents. This approach promotes sustainability and meets the growing demand for environmentally responsible industrial practices. The choice of cashew gum is motivated by its accessibility in industry and its role in facilitating the formation of uniform nanoparticles [10].

To analyze the microwave behavior of materials, planar microwave structures have been utilized due to their ease of fabrication, high sensitivity, adaptability to various substrates, ease of integration, and low cost [1].

This paper combines a sustainable process with the analysis of the loss's properties of materials. The synthesis of nickel and cobalt ferrites was carried out using cashew gum, a renewable polymer that avoids harmful chemicals, highlighting the importance of environmentally responsible practices in the research of new materials. A planar microwave filter with Hilbert fractal geometry was used to analyze the loss behavior of these materials, along with the structural characteristics that may influence their efficiency.

2. Cobalt and Nickel Samples

The synthesis process of cobalt and nickel ferrites was carried out by preparing a stock solution in which 43.8 g of cashew gum (CSG) was dissolved in 200 mL of distilled water, followed by vigorous stirring for 24 hours. Next, the nitrates of iron ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$), cobalt ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and nickel ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were added, forming a homogeneous mixture. The cashew gum organized the micellar network, facilitating the incorporation of atoms and the formation of a uniform structure in the nanoparticles.

After the gel formation, it was subjected to thermal treatment at high temperatures, during which organic residues were removed, and the metal ions were reorganized to form a

crystalline ferrite structure. The cobalt and nickel ferrite nanoparticles were obtained after this treatment.

This green synthesis process utilizing cashew gum resin, extracted from the cashew tree (*Anacardium occidentale*), is sustainable as it avoids harmful chemicals, such as strong acids or bases, and promotes biodegradability by using a natural and renewable material. Thus, cashew gum contributes to the production of advanced materials in an environmentally friendly manner, minimizing environmental impact [10,11].

To study the crystal structure of the nickel ferrite (NFO) and cobalt ferrite (CFO) samples, the diffractograms were refined using CIF cards CoFe_2O_4 (ICSD 109044) and NiFe_2O_4 (ICSD 28108). Rietveld refinement was used, which showed no evidence of secondary phases within the sensitivity of XRD.

The X-ray patterns of the samples were of the non-stoichiometric spinel type, with a 1:1 ratio, possessing a face centered cubic structure and a Bravais lattice Fm-3m. The nomenclature NFO11 refers to the sample containing non-stoichiometric nickel nanoparticles, while the nomenclature CFO11 refers to the non-stoichiometric cobalt samples. Fig. 1 shows the X-ray patterns and Rietveld refinements of the non-stoichiometric CFO11 and NFO11 samples. The blue line indicates the standard diffractogram used for reference. If the peaks of the sample align with the 2θ positions of the standard, the synthesis is considered correct, which is the case here.

Fig. 1 X-ray patterns and Rietveld refinements of non-stoichiometric samples.

3. Filter Design

Microwave filters are crucial for characterizing materials like ferrites, focusing on microwave signal analysis [11]. In the first study, ferrite-polyaniline composites were analyzed using filters to measure attenuation from 8.2 to 12.4 GHz, achieving over 99% attenuation in certain compositions [12]. The second article explores balanced filters designed to

attenuate signals in differential and common modes, improving measurement accuracy by reducing reflections [13]. Together, these filters enhance the precision of microwave losses studies in ferrites, aiding in the analysis of their electromagnetic properties.

The Hilbert fractal curves demonstrate the characteristic of space-filling, allowing them to continuously occupy a limited area without intersecting. Proposed by David Hilbert in 1981, this curve is generated through an algorithm that divides a square into four parts and connects the centers of these squares. This process is repeated indefinitely, resulting in a curve whose total length increases with each iteration [14].

A Hilbert fractal resonator filter of the fourth iteration is employed as the instrument for this analysis. This geometry is widely used in the fabrication of microwave devices, including frequency selective surfaces, antennas, and sensors [15–17]. Its inherent characteristics, such as self-similarity and self-filling, make it a strong candidate for filter miniaturization. It can confine a resonator of considerable length with appropriate coupling between lines within a small area.

Fig. 2 illustrates the microstrip filter design using the fourth iteration of the Hilbert fractal curve as the resonator. The fractal filter was designed and simulated using full-wave electromagnetic simulation software. It has a total length (left) of 243 mm and occupies an area of 20 x 20 mm. The gray area represents the metallic part of the structure.

Fig. 2 - Proposed filter using the fourth iteration of the Hilbert fractal curve.

4. Measurement Procedure

The proposed filter was designed and manufactured using AD1000™ substrate with a dielectric constant of 10.2, loss tangent of 0.0004, and thickness of 1.27 mm. The ports were designed to have impedance characteristic close to 50 Ω and width of 1.1 mm. The prototype filter, was fabricated using the Everprecision® EP2006H prototyping machine.

To analyze the losses behavior of the materials, a square-based support measuring 20 x 20 mm² was placed directly on the resonator, as shown in Fig. 3. Measurements were carried out by placing the CFO11 and NFO11 samples inside this container, separately. It is important to note that the sample size does not affect the precision of the test analysis, as we are

dealing with modifications at the unit cell level. Fig. 4 depicts the filter with the material inserted inside the plastic container.

Fig. 3 – Filter with support

Fig. 4 – Filter with sample

5. Results and Analysis

The crystal structure of the investigated systems exhibits a notable lattice contraction at the edges. Specifically, CFO11 has a unit cell parameter of 8.300 Å, while NFO11 displays a slightly larger unit cell parameter of 8.342 Å, as shown in Table 1. The diameter written in Table 1 refers to the size of the nanoparticles listed in that table. It indicates the measurement of the width of the nanoparticles, expressed in nanometers.

Table 1 – Parameters of the crystal structures of CFO11 and NFO11

Index	Crystallographic parameters				Agreement factors		
	Diameter (nm)	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	R _{wp} (%)	GoF (X ²)	Max delt/sig
CFO11	46.2 [100%]	8.30	8.30	8.30	6.51 8	7.4	1.006
NFO11	69.3 [100%]	8.34 2	8.34 2	8.34 2	7.12 8	9.4 3	0.631

Upon analyzing Table 1, it can be observed that the nickel samples exhibit larger atomic spacing, providing greater freedom of vibration and consequently higher loss compared to the cobalt samples.

Using the microwave filter, the |S₂₁| parameters were obtained with the CFO11 and NFO11 samples placed under the filter, utilizing the Keysight® N9952A vector network analyzer. The results are presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 - Measurement results of the proposed fractal filter with samples CFO11 and NFO11

The S21 graph indicates that nickel ferrites have a higher insertion loss than cobalt ferrites. This is demonstrated by the increased attenuation in the S21 signal for nickel, meaning that less signal is transmitted and more is lost. The measured values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Resonance characteristics of the proposed filter without and with CFO11 and NFO11 samples.

Data	CFO11	NFO11
Frequency (GHz)	1.1	1.1
S21 (dB)	-0.67	-0.88

The S21 parameter, representing the transmitted signal at port 2 relative to the incident signal at port 1, is lower in materials that cause microwave frequency losses. A drop in S21 when the material is placed over the resonator indicates its contribution to signal loss in the filter. In comparing materials, the nickel-based sample shows a lower S21 (-0.88 dB) than the cobalt-based one (-0.67 dB), demonstrating greater microwave loss with nickel. This corresponds with crystal lattice analysis, which reveals that the nickel sample's greater atomic spacing, leading to more significant energy loss when placed over the filter.

Based on the outlined steps and the results obtained, we can compare these results with the existing literature. In [18], the coprecipitation method analyzes the microwave losses of nickel and cobalt ferrites. Our environmentally friendly method uses non-toxic agents to produce nanoparticles. Fig. 5 shows lower transmission loss (less than -2 dB) in the 0.7 to 1.5 GHz range compared to [18], indicating improved transmission efficiency. In [19], ferrite analysis was done at higher frequencies (12-18 GHz), while the proposed study shows better transmission at lower frequencies (below 2 GHz). The proposed study balances controlled losses with transmission efficiency, making it suitable for critical signal passage applications, unlike [19]. Reference [20] studies $\text{NiCoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ with CNFs for X-band but requires an impractical 10.3 mm thickness. The proposed study, with reduced thickness, prioritizes transmission, achieving superior

performance with -2 dB loss in the 1-1.5 GHz range, ideal for efficient signal passage.

6. Conclusion

This paper details the use of a planar fractal filter to examine the losses of nickel ferrite (NFO) and cobalt ferrite (CFO) samples. Both ferrites were studied for their magnetic properties and stability, making them useful in electronics, catalysis, and medicine. The filter geometry, based on the fourth iteration of the Hilbert curve, optimizes the filter area and enhances interaction with the tested samples. The resonance frequency was found to be approximately 1.1 GHz, within a range of 0.7 to 1.6 GHz. Analysis of the crystal lattice showed that atomic spacing impacts vibration capacity and, consequently, the losses of the materials. Measurements for each sample aligned with structural data, supporting theories on materials, and indicated that the nickel sample has a higher insertion loss than the cobalt sample. Additionally, the ferrites were synthesized using a green process involving cashew gum resin, which is biodegradable and renewable. This sustainable approach not only enhances the performance of the ferrites but also reflects a commitment to environmentally responsible practices, underscoring the importance of integrating eco-friendly methods in material science while advancing performance and sustainability.

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